

Investigation study and analysed for an optimum wavelength of FSO Telecommunication System in a weather condition (Fog, Rain, and Snow) with real data applied.

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Abstract:

Modern communication systems adopt the principle of wireless communication as a basic choice in life in the city and nearby offices. Systems are often expensive and monopolized by governments and regimes, so many researchers around the world are interested in finding systems that can be of a cheap nature, have good communication quality, and can send data at an acceptable to excellent rate. Free space optical system is one of those systems that unlicensed and cost-effective system. In this study we found the optimum wavelength for FSO system and apply it with the three main weather condition fog, rain and snow. FSO using many techniques like a LOS (line of sight) and multibeam sending data where voice, video communication and data is achieved with high data rate by bidirectional full duplex connectivity[1]. The 850 nm wavelength is very suitable for FSO system because of it's reliable, high-performance, and inexpensive transmitter and detector components. Also, they are generally available and commonly used in today's service provider networks and transmission equipment[6].

Keywords — Meteorological data, BER, Semiconductor Lasers, short-range application.

I. INTRODUCTION

FSO is Working similarly to OFC (optical fiber cable) but the main difference is the optical light beams are sent through a free atmosphere instead of the fiber optic network using glass fiber. FSO system consists of an optical transceiver that uses the full duplex connection capability. FSO system consists of an optical transceiver that uses the full duplex connection capability. FSO has existed since the 8th century, not a new system, but now is more improved. FSO stands for (free space optical) system consider one of the best optical systems. FSO uses many techniques like LOS (line of sight) and multibeam sending data where voice, video communication, and data are achieved with a high data rate by bidirectional full duplex connectivity[1].

FSO system used the light amplified by a laser to send the data for long distances within the atmosphere or space as a medium. There are many advantages of the FSO system.

They are:

- High flexibility in the system[2].
- Ease of installation less than 30 min in normal situation roof[2].
- Cost-effectiveness system[3].
- straight forward deployment free space optic system. Meaning that no license or frequency coordination between RF systems and microwaves [4].
- High level of security system because of LOS (Line of Site)[4].
- High data rate in comparison with fiber optic system[4].
- No interface with radio frequency[3].
- Low power usage per transmitted bit of system[4].
- Transmission of the optical beam is done by the speed of light; hence it's done in the air[2].

On the other side, there is a limitation that is considered the weak point of the FSO system. They are the challenges as follows:

- Radiation obstructions: birds, tall buildings, and trees can block a single beam[2].
- losses in Geometric: geometric losses mean the shape of the receiver make attenuation by the spreading of the beam and reduced the power level of the signal received[4].
- Atmospheric turbulence: the disturbance that happens due to atmospheric It will affect the power by reducing the received power[3].

Figure 1 The FSO system application.

Because light can travel faster in the air than in the fibreoptic system, it's interesting to study this type of system. The main goal of this paper is to analyze the system with real data values. Control of the output of laser transmitted is important because the signal will be affected by the weather condition and the weather condition will add attenuations to the signal. Therefore, it's important to study the effect of changing power related to weather which is related to the received signal. Furthermore, the models of weather conditions that describe the main weather condition (Fog, Snow, and Rain) have been generated.

Nowadays, several transmission windows are most attracted by telecommunication applications, because of their low attenuation, they are between 780 nm to 1600 nm wavelength range. Most of the applications are used the four common which are 850, 980, 1250, and 1550[5]. In this study, we will focus on them and see the optimum between them in terms of system performance. Then the real data of Ankara city will be applied to it. The 850 nm and 980 nm are very suitable for FSO system operation. It's

reliable, high-performance, and cost-effective in terms of transmitter and receiver[5]. Rarely to use the 1250 window but it has lower power a commercial laser is available. And this wavelength is not that useful for the FSO system[5]. The last one is the 1550 nm is considered one of the best wavelengths of FSO system with low attenuation in the effect of atmosphere and lots of development working nowadays on it.

The semiconductor laser will be the laser used in this paper. It is used widely in telecommunication and especially in FSO systems because it can maintain the wavelength needed in transmission with eye safety international standards and emits a very tiny area of light in one direction that reduces the hazard to humans and animals[5].

Also, a Semiconductor laser is compact in size, rugged, and has low-cost maintenance. Also, the cost of the laser itself is cheap in comparison with other lasers therefore it will affect the cost of the system overall[6].

Figure 2. the attenuation with many important wavelengths in telecommunication.

II. LASER MODEL

Based on equations 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 [6] the output power of the laser will equal to:

$$P_{outB} = \left(\frac{\sigma m}{\sigma m + \sigma i} \right) \frac{h\nu}{q} (I - I_{th}) \quad 1$$

Equation number 1 is will be a derived equation for the internal power of the laser on stimulated emission level[7]. As we know the laser in general will start working to the coherence of light output in the time that the stimulated emission starts.

Next, the laser important formula that will describe the output of the laser based on mirror reflectivity. Depending on the equations 18a, 18b and 18c [8] the laser output formula will be as follow:

$$P_{out} = P_{outB} \left(\frac{((1 - R2^2) * R1)}{((1 - R2^2) * R1) + ((1 - R1^2) * R2)} \right)^2$$

III. SIGNAL MODEL

The received signal power is related to the transmitted power signal. To derive the final received signal we used the Friis equation.

Friis equation: telecommunications engineering famous formula, relates the free space path loss with antenna gains and wavelength into the transmit powers and received.

The received signal [9]:

$P_s = P_{out} * Gr * Gt * Ta * TF * LFS$	3
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The Pout represents the output power

- **Gr**: Transmitter telescope gain
- **Gt**: Receiver telescope gain.
- **Ta**: Atmospheric transmission coefficient
- **TF**: Optical filter transmissivity
- **LFS**: Free-space loss.

Based on equation number 9, 10 and 11 form our previous paper the total Ps will be:

$$P_s = P_{out} * \left(\pi * \frac{D_r}{\lambda} \right)^2 * \left(2 * \pi * \frac{W_t}{\lambda} \right)^2 * Ta * TF * \left(\frac{\lambda}{4 * \pi * L} \right)^2$$

- Dr**: Receiver aperture in cm.
- Wt**: Transmitter aperture in cm.
- L**: Distance in km.

Ta is the atmospheric condition that represents the attenuation due to the weather condition.

IV. WEATHER CONDITION MODEL

In this paper, the main weather condition that will be studied is fog, snow, and rain. There are many models that will be used on to represent the fog but the most used one in the KIM model. For the snow and rain the ITU standard will be used to as model for them. fog is related to visibility, high fog means low visibility, therefore Kim uses this concept to build his model.

Kim model is assuming that there is permitter q that can range of visibility from 0.5 to 50 km. and it's concluded on calculation[10] [6].

$$q = \begin{cases} 1.6 & \text{if } V > 50 \text{ km} \\ 1.3 & \text{if } 6 \text{ km} < V < 50 \text{ km} \\ 0.16V + 0.34 & \text{if } 1 \text{ km} < V < 6 \text{ km} \\ V - 0.5 & \text{if } 0.5 \text{ km} < V < 1 \text{ km} \\ 0 & \text{if } V < 0.5 \text{ km} \end{cases}$$

Figure 3. q Factor with Kim model.

Then the Kim model formula[11] will be:

$$\sigma = \frac{3.912}{V} \left[\frac{\lambda}{550} \right] \tag{5}$$

$$Ta(fog) = e^{\sigma L} \tag{6}$$

Rain & Snow Attenuation:

Next is the rain coefficient[6]

$$Ta(rain) = aR^b \tag{7}$$

And R(mm/h) is will rate of rain in the weather condition[11][6].

Two model used for calculating a and b and the one used here in this paper is the Charbonneau model which a and b are equal to 1.076 and 0.67 respectively.

Snow attenuation [6]:

$$Ta(snow) = aS^b \tag{8}$$

The a and b are equal [6][11]:

	a	b
Wet snow	$0.0001023\lambda+3.7855466$	0.72
Dry snow	$0.0000542\lambda+5.4958776$	1.38

$$SNR = \frac{R * Ps}{\sigma_0 + \sigma_1} \quad 16$$

Total Ta [6]:

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma_{DC} + \sigma_{sh} + \sigma_{BG} \quad 17$$

$$Ta = Ta(snow) * Ta(rain) * Ta(fog) \quad 9$$

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_{DC} + \sigma_{sh} + \sigma_{BG} + \sigma(RIN) + \sigma_{th} \quad 18$$

TF : received telescope constant [9].

V. NOISE MODEL

The noise that will be calculated are:

- Background noise
- Thermal noise
- Dark current
- Relative Intensity Noise (RIN)
- Shot noise

Finally, the BER calculation.

$$BER = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc}\left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} * \sqrt{SNR}\right) \quad 19$$

And their equation as follow respectively[6].

The acceptance values on telecommunication of Bit Error Rate (BER) that consider the system is accepted is 10^{-9} and 10^{-13} [6].

$$PBG = Ar * FOV * \Delta\lambda * TF * Rrad \quad 10$$

VII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

$$\sigma_{BG} = 2q * R * PBG * B \quad 11$$

As mentioned, these papers investigate the four commercial windows of telecommunication. Then apply the real data on chosen optimum wavelength. The next graph (figure 4) will illustrate that 850 nm is the best among all the four wave length in term of distance with a good accepted BER performance. The 850 nm will not be affected by weather condition as the rest of famous windows of wavelength[5].

$$\sigma_{th} = \frac{4 * K * Te * F * B}{RL} \quad 12$$

$$\sigma(RIN) = RIN * ((R)Ps)^2 * B \quad 13$$

Figure 2 illustrate that when increasing the aperture of the transmitter and receiver the distance in general increase and it can be notice that, 850 nm is the best in term of distance with accepted BER.

$$\sigma_{DC} = 2 * q * IDC * B \quad 14$$

$$\sigma_{sh} = 2 * q * R * Ps * B \quad 15$$

Based on that the optimum window that these papers analysed is 850 nm.

RL: load resistance

F: Noise figure.

Te: Equivalent temperature.

B: Electronic bandwidth.

K: Boltzmann's constant

R: detector responsivity.

Ps: received power.

Total cases that have been studied in 850 nm with general assumption are more than 400 cases.

And they are as follow:

VI. BET ERROR RATE AND SIGNAL-TO-NOISE RATIO

Now to check the system performance we need to calculate the BER and normally the calculation of BER need to calculate the SNR. The next equation will be the calculation of SNR[9]

- BER with fog only.
- BER with snow only.
- BER with Rain only.
- BER with Rain and snow.
- BER with Rain with fog.
- BER with fog and snow.
- BER with fog, rain, and snow.

And then applied the real data of Ankara weather condition to get applicable real data.

Figure 8 BER with Distance. For $W_t=20$ cm and $d_r=20$ cm.

The cases that have been studied give some of the important results. That will be as follow:

- It can be confirmed that when increasing transmission aperture means increasing the distance that system can support.

Figure 7 BER with Distance. For $W_t=20$ cm and $d_r=20$ cm. $W_t=10$ cm and $d_r=10$ cm.

- The higher of the receiver antenna aperture the longer distance can pass through the weather conditions.
- The worst case of the study was in 2017 within the past 5 years in Ankara, the system can travel for 1 km with a good BER for $w_t=15$ cm and above.
- In general, the system in normal weather condition with good indication current go for more than 5 km.

Figure 4 a good weather condition with $w_t=0.1$ low fog.

Figure 6 a good weather condition with $w_t=0.2$ low fog.

Figure 5 one of the worst cases that applied.

In this paper there are some fixed values are used to support the formula and they are in the next table:

Table 1 The fixed values that used.

Quantity	Symbol	Value	Unit
Threshold current	I_{th}	0.19	mA
Receiver aperture	d_r	0.05 0.1 0.15 0.2	mm
Transmitter aperture	d_t	0.05 0.1 0.15 0.2	mm
Optical filter transmissivity	TF	0.5	
Earth object blackbody temperature	T	300	K
Load resistance	RL	100	Ω
Circuit noise figure	F	4	
Equivalent temperature	T_e	290	K

As we can see, these values the change of d_r and d_t help us to find our result and make lots of cases to analyze it.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we analyze the 850 nm wavelength because of its recommendation for optical wireless communication and especially for FSO systems [5].

There are four famous optical windows that can be used in FSO systems and they are 1550 nm, 1250, 980, and 850. when the aperture of the transmitter and receiver increases the system performance and the distance that can travel are increased.

Therefore, it's recommended for any feature study to study what's the best value of the receiver and how to improve the distance of the system to let it pass within the bad weather condition.

This study is mainly mathematical study and it's need to be approved in practical way. To give more accurate result and approved result. The Turkish metrological institute support our papers by real value measurement. There are much of hard studies behind the results that have been published to help the designer to build the system and improve it.

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